

TEACHERS' READINESS FOR INTERNATIONAL LARGE-SCALE ASSESSMENTS: EVIDENCE FROM PRIMARY SCHOOLS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This study investigates the instructional readiness of primary school teachers in Uzbekistan with respect to the Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS). Using a descriptive survey design, data were collected from 37 fourth-grade teachers across three regions: Tashkent city (n=15, 40.5%), Samarkand region (n=14, 37.8%), and Namangan region (n=7, 18.9%). Findings reveal that 86.5% of teachers prioritise text comprehension over decoding as their main instructional goal. However, a clear cognitive demand gradient was identified: while lower-order retrieval tasks are consistently used (73.0% always), higher-order evaluative tasks aligned with PIRLS Levels 3–4 are used regularly by only 62.2% of respondents. Additionally, 18.9% of teachers rely predominantly on literary texts, potentially underexposing students to the informational reading demands of PIRLS. Key systemic barriers include time constraints (59.5%), low student motivation (48.6%), and perception of official recommendations as overly idealistic (45.9%). The study provides the first empirical survey-based investigation of teacher readiness for PIRLS in Uzbekistan and proposes recommendations for teacher education reform.*

Keywords: *PIRLS, teacher readiness, reading literacy, primary education, large-scale assessment, Uzbekistan, instructional practice, professional development.*

Introduction. Improving the quality of education has become a priority for many countries. International Large-Scale Assessments (ILSAs) such as the Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS) provide a systematic mechanism for benchmarking student achievement and informing educational policy. PIRLS, conducted every five years by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA), measures fourth-grade students' reading comprehension across literary and informational text types, using a four-level cognitive demand framework: retrieving explicit information, making straightforward inferences, interpreting and integrating ideas, and evaluating and critiquing content (Mullis & Martin, 2019).

Uzbekistan participated in PIRLS for the first time in 2021, marking a significant step in the country's engagement with international educational standards. Alongside this, Uzbekistan's debut in PISA 2022 revealed that student reading literacy scores remained substantially below international averages, raising critical questions about instructional preparedness. In this context, the teacher occupies the most proximal position in students' learning development and is, therefore, central to any reform aimed at improving ILSA outcomes (Leino, Nissinen, & Sirén, 2022).

While a growing body of research addresses student-level PIRLS outcomes and methodological aspects of PIRLS preparation in Uzbekistan (Qorayev & Allayorova, 2021; Shodmonqulova, 2022), survey-based investigations of teachers' instructional readiness — that is, the degree to which their actual classroom practices align with PIRLS cognitive demands —

remain scarce. The present study addresses this gap by examining the instructional orientations, methods, and perceived barriers of primary school teachers in relation to PIRLS requirements.

The study is guided by four research questions: (1) What instructional orientations and methods do primary school teachers use in reading lessons? (2) How consistently do teachers employ tasks aligned with PIRLS cognitive demand levels (L1–L4)? (3) What text types and assessment practices do teachers use? (4) What systemic barriers prevent effective alignment of instruction with PIRLS demands?

Literature Review. PIRLS assesses two primary reading purposes — reading for literary experience and reading to acquire and use information — each evaluated across four cognitive levels. This framework reflects a constructive and interactive view of reading in which students actively construct meaning from texts (Shodmonqulova, 2022). National policy in Uzbekistan has formalised participation in such assessments through Presidential Decree PF-5712 (2019), which set a target of achieving top-30 PISA ranking by 2030, and Government Resolution No. 997 (2018), which institutionalised participation in international assessment programmes.

Teacher quality is a well-established predictor of student reading achievement. Leino, Nissinen, and Sirén (2022), analysing PIRLS 2016 data from four Nordic countries (n=923 teachers, n=17,161 students), found significant associations between instructional quality — including cognitive activation and teacher support — and student reading outcomes. However, a fundamental distinction in the literature separates espoused beliefs from enacted practices (Fang, 1996; Borg, 2003): teachers may report comprehension-oriented goals while delivering predominantly recall-based instruction. Hattie (2009), synthesising over 800 meta-analyses, found that factual recall questioning remains the most prevalent form of classroom discourse globally, with higher-order tasks used comparatively rarely.

In the Uzbek context, the 2022–2023 educational reform introduced "Reading Literacy" as an independent subject in primary schools, signalling institutional recognition of the need to develop comprehension-based reading skills. Qorayev and Allayorova (2021) highlighted the importance of aligning instructional practice with international assessment frameworks, while noting persistent challenges in translating policy intent into classroom reality.

Methods. A descriptive survey design was employed (Creswell, 2014). An electronic questionnaire was administered via Google Forms to primary school teachers across three regions of Uzbekistan: Tashkent city, Samarkand region, and Namangan region. The instrument comprised 16 items covering four dimensions: (1) teacher demographic profile; (2) instructional orientation and methods; (3) practices aligned with PIRLS cognitive demand levels; and (4) text type use, written response assessment, and perceived barriers.

Purposive sampling was used to recruit fourth-grade teachers. Of 42 teachers invited, 37 (88.1%) completed the survey fully. Data were analysed using frequency analysis (absolute counts and percentages). For multiple-response items, each option was counted independently, with percentages calculated relative to the total sample (n=37). Open-ended responses were analysed using content analysis to identify recurring themes. The study adhered to ethical principles of informed consent, anonymity, and voluntary participation.

Results. Participant profile. The sample comprised 37 primary school teachers: Tashkent city (n=15, 40.5%), Samarkand region (n=14, 37.8%), and Namangan region (n=7, 18.9%). The majority were aged 36–45 (48.6%) or 46–55 (29.7%). In terms of qualification category, 45.9% held second-category status, 24.3% first-category, 18.9% the highest category, and 10.8%

specialist status. Teaching experience was predominantly substantial: 40.5% had 21 or more years, 18.9% had 16–20 years, 18.9% had 11–15 years, and 16.2% had 6–10 years (Table 1).

Table 1. Participant demographics (n=37)

Characteristic	Category	n	%
Region	Tashkent city	15	40.5%
	Samarkand region	14	37.8%
	Namangan region	7	18.9%
	Tashkent region	1	2.7%
Age	26–35	4	10.8%
	36–45	18	48.6%
	46–55	11	29.7%
	56 and above	4	10.8%
Qualification	2nd category	17	45.9%
	1st category	9	24.3%
	Highest category	7	18.9%
	Specialist	4	10.8%
Experience	1–5 years	2	5.4%
	6–10 years	6	16.2%
	11–15 years	7	18.9%
	16–20 years	7	18.9%
	21+ years	15	40.5%

Note. Percentages may not sum to 100% due to rounding.

Instructional orientation and methods. When asked about their primary instructional focus, 86.5% (n=32) of teachers reported prioritising text comprehension and critical thinking, while 13.5% (n=5) prioritised fluent and accurate decoding. Regarding the use of innovative methods, 56.8% (n=21) reported regular use and 32.4% (n=12) occasional use; open responses identified specific strategies including the 5H method, Jamburger, BBB method, and Bankomat method.

The most frequently cited teaching methods (multiple responses permitted) were group discussion (70.3%, n=26), text-based question-and-answer (59.5%, n=22), shared reading (48.6%, n=18), independent reading (37.8%, n=14), and reading aloud (29.7%, n=11). Key literacy skills emphasised included creative thinking (81.1%, n=30), text comprehension (78.4%, n=29), vocabulary development (51.4%, n=19), reading speed (40.5%, n=15), and written expression (32.4%, n=12).

Table 2. Teaching methods and literacy skills (multiple responses, n=37)

Item	Response	n	%
Teaching methods	Group discussion	26	70.3%

Item	Response	n	%
	Text Q&A	22	59.5%
	Shared reading	18	48.6%
	Independent reading	14	37.8%
	Reading aloud	11	29.7%
Literacy skills	Creative thinking	30	81.1%
	Text comprehension	29	78.4%
	Vocabulary development	19	51.4%
	Reading speed	15	40.5%
	Written expression	12	32.4%

Note. Percentages exceed 100% as multiple responses were permitted.

PIRLS cognitive demand alignment. Three items assessed practices aligned with the three main PIRLS cognitive demand levels. For explicit information retrieval (PIRLS Level 1), 73.0% (n=27) reported always using such questions, while 27.0% (n=10) reported doing so only sometimes. For inferential tasks (PIRLS Level 2), 89.2% (n=33) affirmed use, with 10.8% (n=4) reporting partial use. Caution is warranted in interpreting this figure, as the survey did not define 'inference' operationally. For evaluating authorial perspective (PIRLS Levels 3–4), 62.2% (n=23) reported regular use, 32.4% (n=12) occasional use, and 5.4% (n=2) rare use — meaning 37.8% did not regularly employ the highest cognitive demand tasks (Table 3).

Table 3. PIRLS cognitive demand practices (n=37)

PIRLS Level	Question	Response	n	%
L1: Retrieve	Q12 – Explicit info	Always	27	73.0%
		Sometimes	10	27.0%
L2: Infer	Q13 – Inference tasks	Yes	33	89.2%
		Partial	4	10.8%
L3–4: Evaluate	Q14 – Author perspective	Regularly	23	62.2%
		Sometimes	12	32.4%
		Rarely	2	5.4%

Note. 37.8% of teachers do not regularly use the highest cognitive demand tasks.

Text types and written response assessment. Regarding text type use, 78.4% (n=29) of teachers reported using literary and informational texts in equal measure, consistent with PIRLS's balanced framework. However, 18.9% (n=7) reported relying predominantly on literary texts, potentially underexposing students to informational reading demands. Concerning the assessment of written constructed responses, 56.8% (n=21) found this moderately difficult, 37.8% (n=14)

found it not difficult, and 5.4% (n=2) found it very difficult — meaning 62.2% found written response assessment at least moderately challenging.

Barriers and theory–practice gaps. The most frequently cited instructional barriers (multiple responses permitted) were time constraints (59.5%, n=22), low student reading motivation (48.6%, n=18), and student text comprehension difficulties (27.0%, n=10). Regarding gaps between theoretical recommendations and classroom practice, 45.9% (n=17) reported that official recommendations are too idealistic to implement, 27.0% (n=10) stated that student levels do not match theoretical expectations, and 21.6% (n=8) cited insufficient teaching resources (Table 4).

Table 4. Instructional barriers and theory–practice gaps (multiple responses, n=37)

Item	Barrier / Gap	n	%
Barriers	Time constraints	22	59.5%
	Low student motivation	18	48.6%
	Text comprehension difficulties	10	27.0%
	Classroom management	2	5.4%
Theory–practice gaps	Recommendations too idealistic	17	45.9%
	Student levels don't match theory	10	27.0%
	Insufficient resources	8	21.6%
	No gap reported	1	2.7%

Note. Percentages exceed 100% as multiple responses were permitted.

Discussion. The findings reveal a complex picture of instructional readiness. The strong comprehension orientation reported by 86.5% of teachers and the predominance of discussion-based methods are encouraging from a PIRLS perspective. However, the study identifies a clear cognitive demand gradient: task frequency declines as cognitive demand increases, with L3–4 evaluative tasks used regularly by only 62.2% of respondents. This pattern is consistent with Hattie's (2009) finding that higher-order tasks remain underrepresented in global classroom practice, and directly affects students' capacity to reach PIRLS's upper benchmark levels (Mullis et al., 2023).

The inferential task result (89.2%) warrants interpretive caution. International research on teacher knowledge of reading consistently shows that teachers without specialist literacy training may conflate simple interpretive questions with genuinely inferential tasks (Fang, 1996). The survey's lack of an operational definition for 'inference' limits the reliability of this figure. The finding that 18.9% of teachers rely predominantly on literary texts constitutes a structural risk, given that PIRLS assesses literary and informational reading in approximately equal proportion (Mullis & Martin, 2019). Informational reading requires distinct skills — understanding expository text structures, domain vocabulary, and information synthesis — that demand dedicated instructional attention.

The most structurally significant finding is that 45.9% of teachers perceive official pedagogical recommendations as too idealistic to implement in practice. This points to a fundamental disconnect between policy intent and classroom reality that is characteristic of educational reform processes in post-transition contexts (Fang, 1996). Addressing this gap requires not only professional development but systemic investment in time, resources, and school-based collaborative learning structures.

Conclusion. This study provides the first survey-based empirical investigation of primary school teachers' instructional readiness for PIRLS in Uzbekistan. Key findings indicate: (1) teachers hold broadly positive comprehension-oriented beliefs, but higher-order evaluative tasks are not regularly used by 37.8%; (2) 18.9% of teachers underexpose students to informational texts; (3) 62.2% find written constructed response assessment at least moderately difficult; and (4) systemic barriers — particularly time constraints (59.5%) and the perceived idealism of official recommendations (45.9%) — impede PIRLS-aligned practice.

These findings carry direct implications for Uzbekistan's educational reform agenda. First, teacher education programmes should explicitly integrate PIRLS cognitive demand frameworks. Second, targeted in-service professional development focused on higher-order comprehension instruction and written response assessment is urgently needed. Third, the curriculum should ensure balanced exposure to literary and informational texts. Fourth, school-based professional learning communities would help bridge the gap between policy recommendations and daily classroom practice. Fifth, PIRLS results should be used diagnostically at school and district level rather than merely as ranking data.

Future research should address the limitations of the present study by employing larger, nationally representative samples, incorporating classroom observation alongside self-report data, and conducting longitudinal evaluation of professional development interventions.

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